

www.arseam.com

International Journal of
Advances in Engineering
& Scientific Research

Academic Research

IN SCIENCE, ENGINEERING, ART & MANAGEMENT

International Journal
of Advances in
Engineering &
Scientific Research
(IJAESR)

ISSN: 2349 –3607 (Online)
ISSN: 2349 –4824 (Print)

Available online at:
<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-4-aug-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and
subscription information:
<http://www.arseam.com/>

NETSTALKER: A PACKET CAPTURE AND ANALYSIS TOOL

Manian V S S #1, Rajath S *2, Nikhil J Agadi *3, Sanjeetha R#4

1,2,3, & 4 M.S. Ramaiah Institute of Technology, Bengaluru, India

Abstract

Packet sniffing is a technique of monitoring every packet that passes through the network. This is unlike standard network hosts that only receive traffic sent specifically to them. The sniffers have the ability to capture all incoming and outgoing traffic. Sniffers also perform extraction of the payload contents and reconstruction of data from the extracted unencrypted content. In theory, it is impossible to detect these sniffing tools because they are passive in nature, meaning that they only collect data and does not alter the contents of the packets. Their ability to eavesdrop on network traffic has made them indispensable for computer administrators. Applications of packet sniffers include forensic analysis to uncover the root cause of network problems, identifying security threats and ensure that data communication and network usage complies with outlined policies. They also assist in statistical analysis of network efficiency and throughput. The statistical reports can be used to diagnose network faults. This research outlines the design and implementation of NetStalker, a passive packet capture and analysis tool.

1. Introduction

Packet sniffers are basically applications that read packets that move from data link, network, transport and application layer depending upon the sniffing mechanism. Basically, the packets are retrieved from the data link layer and the payload is interpreted. An analogy to a packet sniffer is a telephone wiretap. A person can tap a telephone line if he or she wants to snoop on another person. Similarly, packet sniffers can be used to snoop on other people's data that is currently being transmitted across the network. Network sniffers can capture passwords and other sensitive pieces of information. Sometimes, sniffers can retain anonymity if they are launched from another system on the network. The packets may be sniffed from some intermediary hosts to which the launcher has access. Commercial packet sniffers are an indispensable tool used by network administrators to help maintain networks. Typical uses of such sniffing programs include:

- Logging network traffic.

- Solving communication problems.
- Analyzing network performance.
- Retrieving user-names and passwords of users by logging onto the network.
- Detecting network intruders.

Lawful interception of a suspect's personal Internet connection can be a very effective evidence collection mechanism for use in criminal investigations. Packet sniffers can be used to capture the packets being sent from a suspect's personal computer after obtaining the lawful interception warrant. Depending on the type of network, sniffers work differently. The two types of Ethernet environments are:

- Shared Ethernet.
- Switched Ethernet.

In a shared Ethernet environment(Figure 1), all hosts are connected to the same bus and compete with one another, in such scenario packets are broadcasted i.e all machines can receive packets destined for any other machine on the same LAN, in such case installing sniffer on any one of the machine and making it work in promiscuous mode will do the job.

Figure 1: Shared Ethernet Network

An Ethernet environment in which the hosts are connected to a switch instead of a hub is called a switched Ethernet. The switch refers to the table which contains MAC addresses of the LAN segment and then decides the port on which to forward the packets. Switch sends the packet only to the LAN segment having destination computer and does not broadcast, therefore sniffers in such environment cannot work in promiscuous mode.

There are three types of sniffing methods. Some methods work in non-switched networks while others work in switched networks. The sniffing methods are:

- IP-based sniffing.
- MAC-based sniffing.
- ARP-based sniffing.

IP-based sniffing: It works by putting the network card into promiscuous mode and sniffing all packets matching the IP address filter. Normally, the IP address filter isn't set so it can capture all the packets. This method only works in non-switched networks.

MAC-based sniffing: This method works by putting the network card into promiscuous mode and sniffing all packets matching the MAC address filter.

ARP-based sniffing: In this method there is no need to put NIC in promiscuous mode, instead the stateless property of ARP protocol can be used and sniffing can be done in switched environment as well. In order to sniff the packets the ARP packets of both the hosts that are sniffed has to be poisoned by identifying our host to be the intended recipient, when the packet is received by us, the content can be logged and then sent to the actual recipient so that there is no suspicion of the sniffing activity.

2. An Overview of the Shared Ethernet packet sniffing method

The technique behind packet sniffing on shared bus broadcast LANs is explained with the following example. IEEE 802.3 Ethernet LANs employ a broadcast technology, i.e. when a message is sent to

another machine on the LAN, the message is sent to all the machines that are connected to the network. The machine's Network Interface Card (NIC) checks the destination address of the arriving packet [2] [3]. and accepts the packet if it has the latter machine's address; otherwise, it is discarded. A packet sniffer puts the NIC into a "promiscuous mode." The NIC now does not discard packets that are not addressed to its machine. It silently accepts those packets as well.

Before we explain how the NIC is put into a promiscuous mode, let's take a look at a few things about the Ethernet Card. When a machine communicates with another machine on Ethernet media, it specifies the destination machine's Internet Protocol (IP) address and the port number. The IP address (a 32-bit address) specified by the process is converted to that particular card's Media Access Control (MAC) address (a 48-bit low-level address). The packets are then inserted into MAC frames for transmission. Each IP packet is split so that the packets fit into the MAC frames, which contain the destination address. The MAC frames are usually up to 1500 bytes [2] [3]. Note that MAC addresses are unique. Each Ethernet card manufactured contains a unique address that is hard coded into the card. MAC addresses are made up of 48 bits with the first 24 bits specifying the vendor. So all cards manufactured by a specific company will have the same first 24 bits in all their NICs. The next 22 bits specify the serial number of the card, which is assigned by the vendor. Out of the remaining two bits, one bit is used to indicate whether it is a broadcast or a multicast address, and the other bit indicates if any MAC address is locally assigned by system administrator [2][3].

3. The proposed system

NetStalker is a LAN based packet sniffer developed on the Microsoft .NET platform using the WinPcap packet capture and analysis library. NetStalker packet sniffer will provide the following features:

- Identify the network hosts active on the network. This includes details regarding the addresses of the host, the operating system and network traffic information.
- Identify the Ethernet frames passing through the network including the network layer and transport layer protocols and embedded payload.
- Collects the unencrypted text present in the payloads. All the text flowing through the network is analyzed to identify whether they are intelligible or encrypted. The application displays the readable text.
- Displays the images that were sent across the network. This includes the images that are sent to a host when a URL is visited.
- Files that were sent through the network. The application reconstructs files that were sent across the network and stores them.
- Ability to open offline capture sessions. These are files that are dumped by the sniffer. They contain information regarding packets captured during a session. The files must be in the .pcap format.
- Report packet errors which may be identified through checksum.

NetStalker must be run with administrative privileges because the application handles Windows sockets.

4. Architecture

Figure 2: System Components

4.1 User Interface

The NetStalker system provides the user with a rich user interface to control the operations of the sniffer. The application allows the user to select the network adapter that should be used in sniffing, from a list of detected devices. NetStalker displays all captured Ethernet frames in real-time, including their payload in the Hex as well as the ASCII format (provided, the character is printable). Other information provided by the application includes images and reassembled files. The user interface is implemented as a single Windows Form and contains standard controls provided by the .NET framework.

4.2 WinPcap

WinPcap is an open source library for packet capture and analysis for the win32 platforms. WinPcap is the industry-standard tool for link-layer network access in Windows environment. It allows applications to capture and transfer network packets bypassing the protocol stack and has additional useful features like kernel level packet filtering and support for remote packet capture. WinPcap consists of a driver, that extends the operating system to provide low-level network access, and a library that is used to easily access the packets in these layers. The advantages of using WinPcap are - the use of optimizations like kernel-level filtering and buffering for packet capture, ease of programmability and portability. This makes WinPcap superior to comparable approaches [4].

4.3 WinPcap Wrapper

The major components of the WinPcap library are the device driver and the associated DLLs (Dynamic Link Library). The DLLs used by WinPcap are Win32 DLLs. These types of libraries contain machine level code and are primitive. The DLLs used by the .NET framework are quite different from the Win32 DLLs. The .NET DLL is referred to as an assembly. It contains a manifest and metadata along with the CIL (Common Intermediate Language) [5]. Therefore the application cannot make use of the WinPcap library directly. To solve this problem, a wrapper class needs to be created. The function of the wrapper is to expose the unmanaged code in the Win32 DLLs to the .NET framework. The wrapping is achieved using the P/Invoke cross-language interoperability feature of the .NET framework [6]. The wrapper function also handles the data structures used by the Win32 DLL. The remaining components interact with the library through the wrapper.

4.4 Packet Handler

The packet handler is the core of the application and its functionality is critical. The packet handler examines the packet data returned by WinPcap (through the wrapper) to identify the protocol. The packet handler stores each packet into a container specific for each protocol. It maintains the necessary data structures (tree nodes) to graphically represent each captured packet. The captured packet information is used by other modules to perform their function. The operation of the packet handler is event based. The events are generated when a packet is received. On the occurrence of such an event, the packet data is sent to this module by the wrapper.

4.5 Pcap File Handler

The NetStalker application allows its users to work with offline capture sessions. The offline captures are actually files containing information dumped by the sniffer. The application handles only .pcap files. The Pcap format is defined by WinPcap. The .pcap file starts with a section header followed by multiple blocks of data for each captured packet [4]. This feature allows a network administrator to save a capture session for later analysis. Dumping files can be helpful especially when the network load is high. This can reduce the memory usage (physical memory) of the application.

4.6 File assembler

The file assembler is concerned with the reconstruction of files from the available packet payload. The file assembler extracts chunks of data from a TCP session or a UDP packet and attempts to

reconstruct the file. Error is reported if file chunks are missing. The file assembler only attempts reconstruction for certain protocols. They are- HTTP (Hyper Text Transfer Protocol), FTP (File Transfer Protocol), TFTP (Trivial FTP) and SMB (Windows File Sharing) [2] [3].

5. Results

NetStalker was run on a non switched LAN node which used the Realtek RTL8168C(P)/8111C(P) LAN Adapter operating at 100Mbps. An Internet access was made through the node. The following observations were made-

- All hosts that were connected to the node were detected. The following parameters were identified for each host- network address, physical address, hostname, operating system, incoming and outgoing network traffic.
- All captured Ethernet frames were displayed along with the network and transport layer protocol packet headers and payload.
- Files sent through the network were assembled and saved onto the disk.
- All images that were accessed through the network were displayed.
- Readable text in the packet payloads were detected and displayed.
- Errors were reported in the case of unrecognized packets.

Figure 3: Active Hosts and Status

Figure 4: Display of parsed protocol fields for each frame received.

Figure 8: An anomaly log showing errors.

6. Conclusion

NetStalker will be helpful to network administrators who are responsible for the security of the network. This tool also allows administrators to monitor and log network traffic. This tool can also be used as an educational tool to understand the functioning of the network and to have a hands-on experience with different protocols used by different layers of the OSI reference model. The information regarding detected hosts can be used to identify a network security breach (firewall absent/malfunctioning). NetStalker captures all images that were accessed through the network. This can be helpful in identifying policy violations or attempts to view inappropriate content. The interpreted text data from packet payloads allows administrators to be aware of suspicious activities.

7. Future Enhancements

NetStalker is a LAN (shared) based packet sniffer which operates by configuring the network adapters to operate in the promiscuous mode. There exist anti-sniff tools that are meant to detect sniffing activity on a network. One of the ways to identify this is by detecting nodes that are operating in the promiscuous mode. An attacker using an anti-sniff tool can easily know about sniffing activities and time his attack during the period when sniffing is off. Anti-sniff tools can also halt sniffing processes. The application can be modified to run without being detected.

With the advent of Gigabit Ethernet networks, the network bandwidth and speed has risen to levels where it is difficult to capture packets. This is because the rates at which packets are injected into the network exceeds the buffering rate resulting in a lot of packets going unnoticed. One solution to the problem would be to use better buffering techniques. Another method, is to distribute the sniffing activity among multiple nodes, each filtering packets for mutually exclusive IP address ranges.

Advanced network administrators would require facilities to create and inject packets into the network to diagnose network problems at higher layers of the protocol stack.

At present, the NetStalker tool detects only a few basic networking protocols like Ethernet, IPv4, TCP, UDP and ARP, higher layer protocols like HTTP, TFTP, NetBios and DNS. The tool can be extended to support many higher layer protocols.

8. References

- [1] Packet Sniffing: A Brief Introduction paper presented by Sabeel Ansari, Rajeev S.G. and Chandrashekar H.S.
- [2] Communication Networks by Leon Garcia and Indra Widjaja.
- [3] Data Communications and Networking by Behrouz A. Forouzan.
- [4] WinPcap 4.0.2 Product documentation-www.winpcap.org/docs/docs_40_2/html/
- [5] The Complete Reference by Herbert Schildt.
- [6] Microsoft Developers Network Library 2009.